

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379272330>

Synthesis of High-Tg Nonisocyanate Polyurethanes via Reactive Extrusion and Their Batch Foaming

Article in *Macromolecules* · March 2024

DOI: 10.1021/acs.macromol.4c00222

CITATIONS

5

READS

94

6 authors, including:

Arpan Datta Sarma

Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)

9 PUBLICATIONS 90 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Sergei V. Zubkevich

Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)

28 PUBLICATIONS 341 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Frédéric Addiego

Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)

97 PUBLICATIONS 2,712 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Daniel Frederick Schmidt

Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)

120 PUBLICATIONS 3,544 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Synthesis of High- T_g Nonisocyanate Polyurethanes via Reactive Extrusion and Their Batch Foaming

Arpan Datta Sarma, Sergei V. Zubkevich, Frédéric Addiego, Daniel F. Schmidt,* Alexander S. Shaplov, and Vincent Berthé*

Cite This: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.macromol.4c00222>

Read Online

ACCESS |

Metrics & More

Article Recommendations

Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: Polyurethanes (PUs) are common commodity plastics that cover a wide range of applications. However, PUs are based on isocyanates, the toxic compounds that pose respiratory and dermal hazards. As a more sustainable alternative, polyhydroxyurethanes (PHUs) have gained attention as PU substitutes. Nevertheless, their utility is often limited by low molecular weights and inferior properties. To overcome these shortcomings, the present study focuses on the application of reactive extrusion (REx) to the synthesis of thermo-plastic PHUs, allowing rapid production without compromising molecular weight. First, a series of cyclic carbonate monomers were synthesized; in particular, a BPA-based bis(cyclic carbonate) was prepared from the commercial bis(epoxide), while two additional bis(cyclic carbonates) were prepared from the relevant bisphenols via sequential epoxidation and carbonation with CO_2 . Spectroscopic analyses confirm the successful synthesis of high-purity monomers. Second, PHUs were prepared via REx of the synthesized bis(cyclic carbonates) with various diamines following optimization of the process using a model system with the aim of maximizing the molecular weight and yield. The resulting series of linear PHUs possessed molecular weights of up to 21800 g/mol (as assessed via GPC), high strengths (up to 60 MPa as determined by quasi-static tensile testing), and attractive thermal properties (T_g up to 110 °C via DSC; $T_{\text{onset}} > 195$ °C via TGA). The viscoelastic and rheological behavior of selected PHUs is also reported. Finally, PHUs with comparable properties to traditional PUs were foamed, and the resulting foams were shown to possess densities and compressive and thermal properties comparable to conventional rigid PU foams.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polyurethanes (PUs) are nowadays the most versatile and the sixth most widely produced polymer family. PUs find application in many markets, such as coatings, varnishes, elastomers, adhesives, and especially, foams.^{1,2} At the same time, the toxicity of isocyanate monomers is well-established.^{3,4} Exposure to isocyanate vapor can result in severe health effects,^{5–7} and the production of isocyanates generally utilizes even more hazardous phosgene. These concerns resulted in the labeling of various isocyanates in REACH Annex XVII⁸ as carcinogenic, mutagenic, and/or reprotoxic. They have also stimulated active research for safer alternative synthesis and processing routes.^{9–11}

Among synthetic pathways to nonisocyanate PUs, the most studied and promising currently is the step-growth poly-addition of cyclic carbonates and amines, which leads to the formation of polyhydroxyurethanes (PHUs).¹² Many authors have argued that PHUs have the potential to replace traditional PUs.^{12–14} PHUs have been frequently shown to exhibit attractive features including higher resistance to nonpolar solvents, good adhesion, and increased wear resistance.^{3,15}

However, PHUs often suffer from low glass-transition temperature (T_g) values,^{9,16} significant hygroscopicity, and low molecular weights.^{9,13,17,18} These limitations account for the fact that many studies involve the cross-linking of PHUs to improve their properties.¹⁹ However, such cross-links place inherent restrictions on mechanical recycling, thus compromising sustainability.

The use of rigid monomers for the synthesis of high T_g PHUs is relatively infrequent. Reports that describe such efforts are limited to the application of bis(cyclic carbonate) derivatives of bisphenol A diglycidyl ether^{20–22} (Scheme 1A), bisphenol S diglycidyl ether²³ (Scheme 1B), 4-(hydroxymethyl)-2-methoxyphenol diglycidyl ether²⁴ (Scheme 1C), diglycidyl terephthalate^{25,26} (Scheme 1D), hydroquinone diglycidyl

Received: January 26, 2024

Revised: February 27, 2024

Accepted: March 1, 2024

Scheme 1. Examples of Rigid Five-Membered Bis(cyclic carbonate)s, Derivatives of (A) Bisphenol A Diglycidyl Ether, (B) Bisphenol S Diglycidyl Ether, (C) 4-(Hydroxymethyl)-2-methoxyphenol Diglycidyl Ether, (D) Diglycidyl Terephthalate, (E) Hydroquinone Diglycidyl Ether, and (F,G) Divinylbenzene, Used for the Synthesis of Linear PHUs

Figure 1. General scheme of linear PHU synthesis from the aminolysis of bis(cyclic carbonate)s via REX (the presented PHU structure is simplified).

ether²⁰ (Scheme 1E), divinylbenzene²⁷ (Scheme 1F,G), and to selected biobased bis(cyclic carbonate)s.^{28–32}

To improve the low degree of bis(cyclic carbonate)/amine polymerization, many studies have focused on enhanced kinetics or the suppression of side reactions, albeit with limited success. Increasing PHU synthesis temperature enhances reactivity and compensates for viscosity increases during polymerization, but other reports show that the reaction temperature should be kept at ~ 80 °C and should never exceed 120 °C if side reactions are to be avoided.³³ Along these lines, other reports show that, at a temperature of ~ 100 °C and above, the formation of urea moieties occurs,^{34–36} and that, above 120 °C, the rates of other side reactions (e.g., amidation^{9,13}) significantly increase. At temperatures low enough to avoid side reactions, on the other hand, reaction times of hours to days are often required. One reason for this

may be the formation of hydrogen bonds between PHU hydroxyls and carbamate groups,^{17,18,34} which have been hypothesized to induce viscosity increases and limit reactivity.^{34,37} For this reason, the use of hydrogen-bond disruptors (HBDs) has been suggested as a means of improving chain mobility and increasing the degree of polymerization.^{9,34} According to Shaplov et al., the addition of 20–30 wt % of a polar solvent in reactive extrusion (REX) increases the overall homogeneity of the reaction mixture and increases the yields, especially when the temperature of REX is lower than the melting point of at least one monomer.³⁸

Many researchers have taken advantage of the high shear forces associated with REX to polymerize PHUs. This approach enables viscous melts to be processed while ensuring high levels of monomer diffusion^{36,39,40} even for high-melting bis(cyclic carbonate) monomers which are challenging to

handle in batch processes. The polymerization of PHUs by melt processing has been successfully performed by Dubois' team using multifunctional bis(cyclic carbonate) macro-monomers⁴¹ and by Mühlaupt's team using molecular dimers in the presence of catalysts.^{15,39} To the best of our knowledge, however, only one study has reported the use of HBD during the polymerization of PHUs via REx.³⁸

Here, a series of both known and novel bis(cyclic carbonate) monomers have been prepared and reacted with commercial diamines via REx in the presence of 30 wt % of DMSO as the HBD to form linear thermoplastic PHUs (Figure 1). The resultant PHUs have been analyzed in terms of molecular structure, thermal properties, and dynamic thermomechanical properties. A range of PHUs with T_g values as high as 110 °C and molecular weights as high as 21000 g/mol (following 45 min of reaction time) have been produced, with molecular weights of 9700 g/mol accessible even at short reaction times (e.g., 5 min). To further extend this study and evaluate the potential end uses of these PHUs, a vacuum-based lab-scale foaming process was developed and applied to these materials as well. PHU foams thus produced were characterized by evaluations of density, micro-/mesostructure, mechanical resistance, and thermal conductivity. Mechanical strength and thermal transport properties were found to be comparable to those of commercial rigid PU thermoset foams used in the insulation industry, highlighting the potential of high- T_g thermoplastic PHUs in this context.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1. Materials. Phenolphthalein (>99%, Aldrich), 4,4'-(1,1,1,3,3,3-hexafluoropropane-2,2-diyl)diphenol (bisphenol AF, 98%, TCI Europe), epichlorohydrin (99%, Aldrich), diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA, D.E.R. 332, 99%, Aldrich), 3,3'-diamino-*N*-methylpropylamine (DNDPA, 99%, TCI Europe), isophorone diamine (IPDA, Vestamin IPD, 99%, Evonik Industries AG), *p*-diamino dicyclohexyl methane (PACM, Vestamin PACM, 99%, Evonik Industries AG), fatty acid dimer diamine (FADDA, Priamine 1075, 98%, Cargill Corporation), sodium hydroxide (98%, Carl Roth), carbon dioxide (99.7%, Air Liquide), lithium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI, 99%, Solvionic), and anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 99%, Acros Organics) were used as received. Hexamethylenediamine (HMDA, 98%, Sigma) and *p*-xylylenediamine (*p*-XDA, 99%, TCI Europe) were purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Lithium bromide (99%, Acros Organics) was dried at 100 °C/0.5–1 mbar for 10 h in B-585 oven (Buchi Glass Drying Oven, Buchi) filled with P₂O₅ and was then transferred under vacuum inside an argon-filled glovebox (MBRAUN MB-Labstar, H₂O and O₂ content <0.5 ppm). Ultrapure (deionized) water was obtained from an H₂O-II-1-UV-T Arium comfort II UV (Sartorius) purification system.

2.2. Synthesis of Diglycidyl Ethers. Phenolphthalein and bisphenol AF were converted to their diglycidyl ethers by reacting with an excess of epichlorohydrin in the presence of sodium hydroxide in accordance with known procedures,^{42–44} albeit with some adaptations. The typical procedure is given below, using the example of 3,3-bis(4-(oxiran-2-ylmethoxy)phenyl)isobenzofuran-1(3*H*)-one (phenolphthalein diglycidyl ether) synthesis.

2.2.1. Synthesis of Phenolphthalein Diglycidyl Ether (DGEPhPhn). Phenolphthalein (64.5 g, 0.15 mol) and an excess of epichlorohydrin (145.0 g, 1.50 mol) were charged into a 250 mL three-necked flask equipped with a magnetic stirring bar, a thermometer, and a reflux condenser. The reaction mixture was then heated to 95 °C (as monitored by the inserted thermometer) with stirring. NaOH pellets (12.6 g, 0.31 mol) were then added slowly to the reaction mixture (3 pellets/5 min), while paying special attention to the reaction exotherm and adjusting the rate of NaOH addition to avoid a sudden increase of the temperature that might

exceed the boiling point of epichlorohydrin (115 °C). After the complete addition of NaOH (~3 h), the reaction was continued for one additional hour at 95 °C, followed by cooling of the reaction mixture to RT. The reaction mixture was filtered off, and the resulting solution was washed with ultrapure water in a separatory funnel (3 × 40 mL). The excess epichlorohydrin was then removed at 100 °C/0.5–1 mbar, and the residue was further dried at 150 °C/0.5–1 mbar for 8 h to yield DGEPhPhn in the form of a light-yellow solid mass. Yield: 47.0 g (73%); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.92 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 7.85–7.78 (m, 2H), 7.66 (ddd, *J* = 8.0, 6.5, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 7.23–7.15 (m, 4H), 7.00–6.92 (m, 4H), 4.32 (ddd, *J* = 11.4, 2.7, 1.1 Hz, 2H), 3.82 (dd, *J* = 11.4, 6.5 Hz, 2H), 3.32–3.28 (m, 2H), 2.83 (dd, *J* = 5.1, 4.2 Hz, 2H), 2.69 (dd, *J* = 5.1, 2.6 Hz, 2H).

2.2.2. Synthesis of Bisphenol AF Diglycidyl Ether (DGEBAF). DGEBAF was obtained similar to DGEPhPhn in the form of a light-yellow solid mass. Yield: 45.0 g (69%); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.24 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 4H), 7.13–6.98 (m, 4H), 4.37 (dd, *J* = 11.3, 2.7 Hz, 2H), 3.88 (dd, *J* = 11.3, 6.5 Hz, 2H), 3.34 (ddt, *J* = 6.7, 4.6, 2.7 Hz, 2H), 2.85 (t, *J* = 4.7 Hz, 2H), 2.72 (dd, *J* = 5.1, 2.6 Hz, 2H).

2.3. Synthesis of bis(cyclic carbonate)s. The five-membered bis(cyclic carbonate)s were obtained from the diglycidyl ethers of bisphenol A (DGEBA), bisphenol AF (DGEBAF), or phenolphthalein (DGEPhPhn) by their reaction with gaseous CO₂^{15,21,39,45,46} in anhydrous DMSO in the presence of anhydrous LiBr as a catalyst. The typical procedure is provided below by an example of 4,4'-(((propane-2,2-diylbis(4,1-phenylene))bis(oxy))bis(methylene))bis(1,3-dioxolan-2-one) (bisphenol A bis(cyclic carbonate)) synthesis.

2.3.1. Synthesis of Bisphenol A Bis(cyclic carbonate) (CCBA). The carbonation reaction was carried out using a 500 cm³ Buchiglasuster (Polyclave) reactor equipped with a mechanical stirrer and a Huber (Petite Fleur) heating/cooling device. DGEBA (60.0 g, 0.176 mol) was charged into the reactor, which was further evacuated and flashed with argon. Anhydrous DMSO (150 mL) was charged into the reactor using a cannula, and mixing was continued until a homogeneous single-phase reaction mixture was realized. A catalytic amount of anhydrous LiBr (1.5 g, 17.62 mmol, 10 mol %) was weighed separately in the Schlenk flask inside the glovebox and was dissolved in 50 mL of anhydrous DMSO on stirring. The LiBr solution was then added to the DGEBA solution in the reactor via syringe injection. After stirring for 10 min at room temperature, the inert atmosphere of the reactor was replaced with CO₂ via evacuation at RT and direct connection of a CO₂ cylinder to the reactor while maintaining an internal pressure of 1 bar. The temperature of the reactor was then increased to 80 °C while continuously stirring its contents with a turbine-type blade at 250 rpm. After reaching the reaction temperature of 80 °C, the CO₂ pressure inside the reactor was increased to 2 bar, and the reaction was continued at 80 °C for another 72 h. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled to RT, and the product was precipitated in 2 L of deionized water. The precipitate was collected by filtration, placed back into the flask, and thoroughly washed with 2 L of deionized water on stirring. This procedure was repeated thrice. After the final washing with water, the product was collected by filtration, dried at RT for 2–3 h, and further at 100 °C/0.5–1 mbar for 12 h to yield CCBA in the form of a white crystalline powder. Yield: 72.3 g (95.8%); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.16–7.08 (m, 4H), 6.90–6.82 (m, 4H), 5.18–5.07 (m, 2H), 4.62 (t, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 4.37 (dd, *J* = 8.4, 5.9 Hz, 2H), 4.24 (dd, *J* = 11.3, 2.6 Hz, 2H), 4.16 (dd, *J* = 11.3, 4.6 Hz, 2H), 1.58 (s, 6H); IR (KBr pellet): 3067 (w, ν_{CH} (Ph)), 2983 (m, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 2933 (w, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 2883 (w, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 1789 (vs, ν_{C=O}), 1607 (m, ν_{aryl}), 1583 (w, ν_{aryl}), 1511 (s, ν_{aryl}), 1477 (m), 1461 (w), 1402 (m), 1389 (m), 1367 (m), 1337 (w), 1296 (w), 1247 (s, ν_{C-O-C} (Ph-O-R)), 1179 (vs, ν_{C-C} (Ph-C-C-Ph)), 1106 (s, ν_{C-O-C}), 1062 (s, ν_{C-O-C}), 1013 (w), 996 (m), 851 (w), 827 (m, ν_{CH} (*p*-Ph)), 773 (m), 713 (m), 623 (w), 584 (m), 549 (w) cm⁻¹; *T*_m (DSC, 5 °C/min) = 159.1 °C; *T*_g (DSC, 5 °C/min) = 32.3 °C; Anal. Calcd for C₂₃H₂₄O₈ (428.44): C, 64.48%; H, 5.65%. Found: C, 64.15%; H, 5.90%.

2.3.2. Synthesis of Bisphenol AF Bis(cyclic carbonate) (CCBAF). The CCBAF monomer was prepared following the procedure

presented for CCBA synthesis. The product obtained after purification with deionized water was dried, redissolved in dichloromethane, and precipitated in the excess of diethyl ether. The solid was collected by filtration and dried at 100 °C/0.5–1 mbar for 12 h to yield CCBAF in the form of a solid beige mass which was ground by hand using a mortar and pestle to produce a light beige powder. Yield: 35%; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.27 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 4H), 7.07 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 4H), 5.18 (dddd, *J* = 8.6, 6.1, 4.4, 2.5 Hz, 2H), 4.65 (t, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 4.42 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 5.9 Hz, 2H), 4.35 (dd, *J* = 11.3, 2.6 Hz, 2H), 4.27 (dd, *J* = 11.2, 4.5 Hz, 2H); ¹⁹F NMR (565 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ -65.83; IR (KBr pellet): 3056 (w, ν_{CH} (Ph)), 2991 (w, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 2933 (w, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 2880 (w, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 1795 (vs, ν_{C=O}), 1613 (s, ν_{aryl}), 1587 (w, ν_{aryl}), 1517 (s, ν_{aryl}), 1482 (m), 1459 (m), 1424 (w), 1401 (m), 1366 (w), 1330 (w), 1299 (m), 1257 (vs, ν_{C-O-C} (Ph-O-R)), 1207 (s, ν_{CF}), 1172 (vs, ν_{C-C} (Ph-C-C-Ph)), 1134 (m, ν_{CF}), 1105 (m, ν_{C-O-C}), 1090 (w), 1053 (s, ν_{C-O-C}), 993 (m), 967 (m), 952 (w), 928 (m), 829 (s, ν_{CH} (*p*-Ph)), 773 (m), 746 (w), 736 (m), 714 (w), 703 (m), 650 (w), 637 (w), 546 (w), 532 (w) cm⁻¹; T_g (DSC, 5 °C/min) = 44.8 °C; Anal. Calcd for C₂₃H₁₈F₆O₈ (536.38): C, 51.50%; H, 3.38%. Found: C, 51.26%; H, 3.59%.

2.3.3. Synthesis of Phenolphthalein Bis(cyclic carbonate) (CCPhPhn). The CCPhPhn monomer was prepared following the procedure presented for CCBA synthesis. The product obtained after purification with deionized water was dried, redissolved in dichloromethane, and precipitated in the excess of ethanol. The solid was collected by filtration and dried at 100 °C/0.5–1 mbar for 12 h to yield CCPhPhn in the form of a solid yellow mass which was ground by hand using a mortar and pestle to produce a light yellow powder. Yield: 40%; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.93 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 7.87–7.81 (m, 2H), 7.66 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 1H), 7.23 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 4H), 6.98 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 4H), 5.15 (dtd, *J* = 11.1, 5.1, 2.6 Hz, 2H), 4.62 (t, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 4.38 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 5.9 Hz, 2H), 4.29 (dt, *J* = 11.1, 2.1 Hz, 2H), 4.21 (dd, *J* = 11.3, 4.6 Hz, 2H); IR (KBr pellet): 3043 (w, ν_{CH} (Ph)), 2984 (w, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 2925 (w, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 2887 (w, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 1795 (vs, ν_{C=O}), 1759 (vs, ν_{C=O}, lactone), 1608 (s, ν_{aryl}), 1584 (w, ν_{aryl}), 1517 (vs, ν_{aryl}), 1465 (m), 1398 (m), 1364 (w), 1334 (w), 1290 (s), 1251 (vs, ν_{C-O-C} (Ph-O-R)), 1176 (vs, ν_{C-C} (Ph-C-C-Ph)), 1104 (s, ν_{C-O-C}), 1086 (s), 1051 (s, ν_{C-O-C}), 1016 (w), 990 (w), 964 (m), 946 (w), 926 (m), 876 (w), 833 (s, ν_{CH} (*p*-Ph)), 801 (m), 762 (s), 725 (w), 713 (w), 692 (s), 630 (w), 613 (w), 540 (m), 512 (w) cm⁻¹; T_g (DSC, 5 °C/min) = 79.3 °C; Anal. Calcd for C₂₈H₂₂O₁₀ (518.47): C, 64.86%; H, 4.28%. Found: C, 64.90%; H, 4.44%.

2.4. Synthesis of PHUs by REx. PHUs were synthesized by REx using a 15 cm³ microcompounder (Xplore MC 15 HT, Figure S13) equipped with two conical corotating intermeshing screws (Figures 1 and S13). The respective bis(cyclic carbonate) and diamine were combined at a 1:1 molar ratio, and anhydrous DMSO was added as the HBD. The reaction time was varied from 1 to 270 min to synthesize PHUs with different molecular weights. After the completion of the reaction, the reactive mass was dissolved in DMSO, precipitated into a nonsolvent (ethyl acetate for CCBA-HMDA, CCBA-DNDPA, CCBA-pXDA, CCBAF-pXDA, and CCPhPhn-pXDA PHUs, water for CCBA-PACM and CCBA-IPDA PHUs, or ethanol for CCBA-FADDA PHU), washed with the same nonsolvent, and dried under vacuum. The assigned NMR spectra of polymers (Figures S15–S24) as well as their DSC (Figures S28–35), TGA (Figure S27), DMTA (Figure S36), and stress–strain (Figure S37) plots can be found in the Supporting Information. The typical polycondensation procedure is provided below using the example of CCBA-HMDA synthesis.

2.4.1. Synthesis of CCBA-HMDA PHU. Before charging the CCBA and HMDA monomers, the barrel temperature of the microcompounder (Xplore MC 15 HT) was set to 103 °C to maintain a melt temperature of 100 °C throughout the process under flowing argon (50–100 mL/min). An inert atmosphere inside the microcompounder was further maintained throughout the entire reaction process. Following these preparatory steps, CCBA (6.00 g, 0.014 mol), HMDA (1.63 g, 0.014 mol), and a HBD additive (anhydrous

DMSO, 2.28 g, 30 wt % with respect to the overall monomer content) were combined within the hopper of the feeding tool (Figure S14) and were charged into the preheated microcompounder. The reaction was continued for 2.5 h at 100 °C using the recirculating feature of the microcompounder and maintaining a constant screw speed of 120 rpm. Following the completion of the reaction, the melt was redirected to the die and was extruded. The CCBA-HMDA polymer was dissolved in DMSO and purified by precipitation into an excess of ethyl acetate. The product, in the form of a yellow sticky mass, was collected after decantation, extensively washed with ethyl acetate, and dried at 110 °C/0.5–1 mbar for 12 h to yield PHU in the form of yellow powder. Yield: 4.88 g (64%); M_n (GPC) = 19000 g/mol, M_w/M_n = 2.3; T_g (DSC, 5 °C/min) = 58.6 °C, T_g (DSC, 10 °C/min) = 57.2 °C; T_{onset} (TGA, 5 °C/min) = 195 °C; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.15 (dt, *J* = 35.6, 5.8 Hz, 2H), 7.08 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 4H), 6.81 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 4H), 5.20 (d, *J* = 4.6 Hz, 1.4H), 4.90 (s, 0.49H), 4.85 (q, *J* = 5.3 Hz, 0.46H), 4.11–3.81 (m, 8.67H), 3.56 (t, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 2.93 (q, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 4H), 1.56 (s, 6H), 1.40–1.30 (m, 4H), 1.21 (s, 4H); IR (KBr pellet): 3414 (s, ν_{OH}), 3331 (s, ν_{NH}), 3059 (w, ν_{CH} (Ph)), 3038 (w, ν_{CH} (Ph)), 2962 (m, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 2936 (s, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 2869 (m, ν_{CH} (CH)₂), 1701 (vs, ν_{C=O}, amide I), 1608 (m, ν_{aryl}), 1535 (s, ν_{NH}, amide II), 1511 (vs, ν_{aryl}), 1462 (m), 1413 (w), 1362 (w), 1330 (w), 1286 (vs, ν_{CO}), 1247 (vs, ν_{C-O-C} (Ph-O-R)), 1184 (vs, ν_{C-C} (Ph-C-C-Ph)), 1146 (m), 1106 (m, ν_{C-O-C}), 1044 (s), 1013 (w), 955 (w), 880 (w), 830 (s, ν_{CH} (*p*-Ph)), 775 (m), 730 (w), 661 (w), 640 (w), 573 (m) cm⁻¹.

2.5. Characterization. **2.5.1. Spectral Properties.** NMR spectra were recorded on an Avance III HD 600 MHz spectrometer (Bruker) at 25 °C in the indicated deuterated solvent and are listed in ppm. The signals corresponding to the residual protons and carbons of the deuterated solvent were used as an internal standard for ¹H and ¹³C NMR, respectively. C₆F₆ (−164.9 ppm) was utilized as an external standard for ¹⁹F NMR. All ¹H NMR were acquired in DMSO-*d*₆ except those for FADDA and its derivatives, where CDCl₃ was used instead.

Fourier transformed infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was performed using an INVENIO R (Bruker) instrument and KBr pellets. All spectra were taken over a range of 4000–500 cm⁻¹, collecting 64 scans at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

2.5.2. Molar Mass. Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) was applied to determine the number-average (M_n) and weight-average (M_w) molecular weights as well as the M_w/M_n ratio of the PHUs. This was performed using a 1200 Infinity gel permeation chromatograph (Agilent Technologies) equipped with a PL PolarGel-L column, a PL PolarGel-M guard column (Agilent Technologies), and an integrated refractive index detector. A 0.1 M solution of lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide in DMF served as an eluent at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min at 50 °C. PMMA standards (PMMA EasiVial, Agilent Technologies, M_p = 550–1558000 g/mol) were used for calibration.

2.5.3. Thermal Properties. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) for both monomers and polymeric samples was performed using a DSC 300 Caliris Select instrument (NETZSCH) in the range of −80–190 °C at a rate of 5 °C/min (first cycle) and 10 °C/min (second cycle) under N₂ atmosphere. Two heat–cool cycles were carried out for each sample. Glass transition temperatures (T_g) were calculated from the second heating curve by the shift of the baseline of the DSC data.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out in air on a TGA 2 Star[®] system (Mettler Toledo), applying a heating rate of 5 °C/min. The onset weight loss temperature (T_{onset}) was determined as the point in the TGA curve at which a significant deviation from the horizontal was observed. The resulting temperature was then rounded to the nearest 5 °C.

2.5.4. Mechanical Properties. All polymeric samples for rheological, tensile, and dynamic mechanical thermal studies were prepared using a vacuum compression molding device (VCM Essentials, MeltPrep, Figure S26). The device was preheated to the molding temperature (T_{molding} = PHU T_g (as determined by DSC) + 50 °C), and vacuum compression molding was performed using the

Table 1. Properties' Summary for all PHUs Synthesized by REx (100 °C, 120 rpm, 2.5 h)

PHU	Polymer Synthesis			Polymer Properties								
	Bis(cyclo-carbonate)	Diamine	Yield (%) ^d	M_n^b (g/mol)	M_w/M_n^b	T_{onset}^c (°C)	T_g^d (°C)	T_α^e (°C)	E^f (GPa)	σ_1^g (MPa)	ϵ^h (%)	E^i (GPa)
CCBA-FADDA			65	17,200	2.1	245	25	35	0.77	8.8 (± 1.5)	300 (± 28)	0.021 (± 0.002)
CCBA-DNDPA			80	21,800	3.2	195	58	65	2.10	48.3 (± 7.0)	2.7 (± 0.1)	2.5 (± 0.6)
CCBA-HMDA			64	19,000	2.3	195	59	73	1.42	16.7 (± 1.0)	3.0 (± 0.1)	0.9 (± 0.1)
CCBA-PACM	CCBA		47	5,200	2.0	195	97	<i>j</i>	<i>j</i>	<i>j</i>	<i>j</i>	<i>j</i>
CCBA- <i>p</i> -XDA			80	14,500	2.1	210	80 (110) ^k	72	1.42	43.2 (± 4.4)	1.4 (± 0.2)	2.5 (± 0.3)
CCBA-IPDA			72	4,700	2.0	205	101	<i>j</i>	<i>j</i>	<i>j</i>	<i>j</i>	<i>j</i>
CCBAF- <i>p</i> -XDA	CCBAF	<i>p</i> -XDA	65	13,200	1.9	230	102	88	1.88	61.6 (± 7.5)	2.5 (± 0.7)	2.4 (± 0.5)
CCPhPhn- <i>p</i> -XDA	CCPhPhn	<i>p</i> -XDA	80	10,000	3.0	220	110	92	2.96	56.0 (± 1.5)	1.9 (± 0.1)	3.4 (± 0.4)

^aIsolated yield. ^bBy GPC/SEC in 0.1 M LiTFSI in DMF at 50 °C calibrated using PMMA standards. ^cOnset mass loss temperature by TGA on air at a heating rate of 5 °C/min. ^dBy DSC at a heating rate of 5 °C/min. ^eTaken from the peak in the loss modulus (E'') curve as measured at a heating rate of 3 °C/min. ^fStorage modulus at 25 °C. ^gTensile strength. ^hElongation at break. ⁱTensile modulus. ^jThe samples were too brittle for DMTA studies or tensile testing. ^kMelting point by DSC at a heating rate of 5 °C/min.

relevant metal sample chamber with a PTFE insert for 5 min at 1 bar. Following processing at an elevated temperature, specimens were cooled to ambient temperature over the course of 5 min while inside the mold with a pressure of 1 bar maintained to ensure dimensional stability. Unless otherwise indicated, all specimens were conditioned for at least 24 h at 22 °C inside a desiccator to avoid any water uptake and then removed immediately prior to testing.

Rheological measurements were performed using a Physica MCR 302 rheometer (Anton Paar) equipped with a CTD 450 temperature control unit. Experiments were carried out using 25 mm diameter disposable aluminum parallel plate fixtures and operating in shear mode. Specimens were made with 0.60 ± 0.01 g of PHU via vacuum compression molding following the same protocol as indicated above. Rheological studies were done using disk-shaped specimens with diameters of 25 mm and thicknesses of 1.1 ± 0.1 mm. The gap between the plates was maintained at 1 ± 0.1 mm during the experiment. The instrument was preheated to 125 °C prior to loading of the sample, and a 3 min isothermal hold was performed following sample loading but before the start of any experiment to ensure uniform specimen temperature. Rheological measurements were recorded at a fixed temperature of 125 °C with a controlled strain of 0.1% while performing a frequency sweep in the range of 0.1–100 rad/s.

The quasi-static mechanical properties of PHUs were tested using an Instron 5967 universal testing machine (UTM, Instron Corporation) with a 1 kN load cell operated in tension mode. Tensile testing was performed on Type 4 specimens, as specified by the ISO 37 standard. Specimens were made with 0.16 ± 0.01 g of polymeric material via vacuum compression molding following the same protocol as indicated above. Unless otherwise indicated, all specimens were conditioned for at least 24 h at 22 °C inside a desiccator to avoid any water uptake and then removed immediately prior to testing. Mechanical tests were performed at room temperature (21 ± 2 °C) and a relative humidity of $50 \pm 5\%$. The crosshead speed was maintained at 5 mm/min during all experiments. To achieve statistically valid results, a set of three specimens was tested for each polymeric material (Table 1). The tensile modulus was

measured from the stress–strain plots within the Hookean region (0.1–0.2% strain) with the help of Bluehill Universal (v 4.09) software.

Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) of PHUs was carried out using a GABO Eplexor 500N instrument (Netzsch-Gerätebau GmbH) operating in tension mode (dynamic strain: 0.25%, pretension (preload force): 0.08 N, static strain of 1%). DMTA was performed on rectangular bar-shaped specimens (approximate length \times width \times thickness = $20 \times 5 \times 1$ mm) prepared from 0.12 ± 0.01 g of polymeric material via vacuum compression molding, following the same protocol as indicated above. Experiments were performed at 1 Hz frequency with a heating rate of 3 °C/min from -50 to 120 °C. Storage and loss moduli (E' and E'') were recorded in this way, as well as the damping parameter or loss factor ($\tan \delta$), defined as the ratio $\tan \delta = E''/E'$. While it is common practice to determine T_α based on the $\tan \delta$ peak, here T_α is derived from the loss modulus peak, in line with multiple reports specifically recommending this as the more rigorous and appropriate approach for properly defining the main relaxation temperature.^{47,48}

2.6. Fabrication and Testing of Foams from Linear PHUs.

Synthesized PHUs were foamed using vacuum compression molding at an elevated temperature.⁴⁹ A detailed description of the equipment is given in the Supporting Information (Figure S38). Depending on the desired density of the final foam, a required amount of PHU (1–2 g) was combined with a minimum amount of acetone (~ 1 g of polymer in ~ 1.5 mL of acetone) to achieve a homogeneous mixture which was placed in a specially designed PTFE mold having a volume of 30 mL and equipped with a perforated lid (3–5 holes of 2 mm diameter). The set temperature for the foaming procedure was adjusted to ~ 5 °C lower than T_g of the PHU being foamed. The foaming procedure was completed within 4–6 h while applying a dynamic vacuum of 0.5–1 mbar configured with a liquid nitrogen-cooled solvent trap. The density of the resulting foam was confirmed by dividing the weight of the final foam by the mold volume (30 mL).

2.6.1. Microcomputed X-ray Tomography. To observe the internal structure of the foams, entire foamed specimens (30 mL) were analyzed by microcomputed X-ray tomography (μ CT). The

Scheme 2. General Scheme for the Preparation of Bis(cyclic carbonate)s

μ CT equipment used was an EasyTom 160 (RX Solutions) equipped with a microfocused tube (small focus spot mode). X-rays were generated using a tungsten source energized at 60 kV and 120 mA. The source-to-detector distance and the source-to-object distance were set to 62 and 315 mm, respectively, resulting in a voxel size of $\sim 25 \mu\text{m}$. For each as-processed sample, its overall volume was analyzed, enabling the visualization of the entirety of its internal structure. A 16 bit flat panel imager with a total pixel area of 1920×1536 pixels served as the detector. Each projection was recorded over the course of 2 s, and a total of 1440 projections were recorded over 360° with a step size of 0.25° . The 3D reconstruction of the sample volume into stacked slices was performed by means of the Xact64 software package (RX Solutions, Chavanod, France). The extraction of stacked slices was achieved after applying a series of corrections to the 1440 projections, including a sample movement correction (spot deviation module), a system misalignment correction (geometry correction module), and a ring filter (5 pixels). The 3D image analysis of the stacked slices was done with the Avizo software package (Konrad-Zuse-Zentrum Berlin/FEI SAS-Thermo Fisher Scientific). In particular, the following procedure was utilized: three subvolumes of $500 \times 500 \times 166$ pixels were extracted from the overall sample volume; the subvolumes were corrected through the application of a median filter (3D interpretation, neighborhood connectivity of 6, and three iterations) to facilitate grayscale segmentation; the objects of interest (pores or matrix) were extracted from the subvolumes by means of segmentation; insignificant small objects were eliminated from the slices to improve the object quantification accuracy (3D interpretation and 10 pixel maximum size for removal); and finally the pores were quantified in three dimensions. The pore volume fraction and the average equivalent pore diameter were calculated, and histograms of the equivalent pore diameter distribution were extracted and interpreted based on the skewness. The equivalent diameter (D_{eq}) and skewness (G_1) are determined using the following equations

$$D_{\text{eq}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{6V}{\pi}} \quad (1)$$

$$G_1 = \frac{\sqrt{n(n-1)}}{n-2} \left[\frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^3}{\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2\right)^{3/2}} \right] \quad (2)$$

where V is object volume, n is the sample size (number of heterogeneities to be analyzed), x_i is the set of all sampled equivalent pore diameter values, and \bar{x} represents the sample mean equivalent pore diameter.

2.6.2. Thermal Conductivity. The thermal conductivity of PHU foams was measured at room temperature ($21 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) with a Hot Disk TPS 2500S instrument (Hot Disk AB).⁵⁰ To minimize measurement errors due to foam inhomogeneity, measurements were made with both the upper and lower surfaces of the foam in contact with the Hot Disk sensor (sensor number: 8563, 9.9 mm diameter, and Kapton-coated). To achieve statistically valid results, this was repeated with two different pieces of foam, resulting in a

minimum of four measurements. The close contact between the foams and the sensor was ensured by the adjustment screw on the top of the sample holder.

2.6.3. Mechanical Properties. The mechanical performance of the produced foams was studied with an Instron 5967 universal testing machine (UTM, Instron Corporation) in a compression mode. The samples were placed between the platens of the UTM, and a compression rate of 2.5 mm/min was applied until a compressive strain of 15% was reached. A 1 kN load cell was used to measure the mechanical response of each foam. After compression testing, the foams were taken out of the UTM and allowed to stand at $21 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $50 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity for 1 h. The permanent deformation was then measured as a percentage of the ratio of change in height of the sample to the original height. Two specimens of each composition were tested to ensure the repeatability of the test.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Design and Synthesis of Bis(cyclic carbonate) Monomers. Currently, there are no commercial bis(cyclic carbonate) monomers available on the market. Thus, the work started with the selection of monomeric structures with the goal of realizing maximum rigidity in the bis(cyclic carbonate) component to compensate for the requirement to use aliphatic (and therefore less rigid) diamines. Such combinations are intended to ensure appropriate reactivity and enable the formation of PHUs with high ($\geq 70^\circ\text{C}$) glass-transition temperatures as well as good processability and solubility in common organic solvents. As high-molecular PHUs can only be synthesized from more reactive aliphatic diamines,^{12,13} bis(cyclocarbonate) should contain aromatic rings to provide the desired T_g values. As a first monomer, bisphenol A bis(cyclocarbonate) (Scheme 2, CCBA) was selected due to the availability of high-purity DGEBA and the rigidity of the structure, as well as the expectation that this would result in PHUs readily soluble in organic solvents by analogy with other classes of BPA-based polymers.⁵¹ The bisphenol AF bis(cyclic carbonate) (Scheme 2, CCBAF) was chosen for its rigidity and solubility as well as the increased T_g of the polymers bisphenol AF yields in comparison with bisphenol A.⁵² Finally, phenolphthalein bis(cyclic carbonate) (Scheme 2, CCPhPhn) was selected as the representative of the monomers that led to the formation of the so-called cardo-polymers (the term introduced by Vygodskii and Salazkin),^{53,54} where cyclic units are fused to a single atom within the backbone of the polymer chain. The presence of cardo groups such as the lactone cycle of CCPhPhn in heterochain polymers endows them with enhanced thermal stability, together with excellent solubility and high T_g .^{53,55}

The general synthetic pathway for the preparation of designed bis(cyclic carbonate)s from the respective bisphenols

Figure 2. ^1H NMR spectra of bis(cyclic carbonate) monomers, initial bisphenols, and bis(epoxide)s; (a) ^1H NMR spectra of CCBA and DGEBA; (b) ^1H NMR spectra of CCBAF, DGEBAF, and bisphenol AF; (c) ^1H NMR spectra of CCPhPhn, DGEPhPhn, and phenolphthalein. (Initial bisphenols and bis(epoxide)s are shown for comparison; enlarged and detailed spectra are shown in Figures S5–S7.)

or diglycidyl ethers is shown in Scheme 2. First, the bisphenol of choice (phenolphthalein or bisphenol AF) was converted to the respective bis(epoxide) by the well-known reaction involving an excess of epichlorohydrin in the presence of sodium hydroxide.^{42–44} The second step consisted of the reaction of bisphenol diglycidyl ether with CO_2 under 2 bar

pressure in the presence of lithium bromide as the catalyst.^{15,21,39,45,46} Anhydrous DMSO was chosen as the additive in the latter reaction given its low toxicity and minimal volatility at 80 °C. The completion of the reaction was monitored via ^1H NMR spectroscopic studies assessing the extent of conversion at 12 h intervals. It was found that a nearly

quantitative conversion of epoxide to cyclic carbonate groups was achieved after 72 h.

The bis(epoxide) and bis(cyclic carbonate) monomers were subjected to NMR (Figures 2 and S1–S3, S5–S7) and FTIR (Figures 3 and S8, S9) analyses at each step of synthesis to

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of bis(cyclic carbonate)s and DGEBA, with selected assignments highlighted (for more detailed assignments, see Figures S8 and S9).

confirm their chemical structure and purity. ^1H NMR spectra of all monomers are shown in Figure 2a–c along with those of the starting materials (bis(phenols)) and intermediate products (diglycidyl ethers). For DGEBAF and DGEPhPhn (Figure 2b,c), the disappearance of the OH signal at 9.8 ppm along with the appearance of new signals at 3.8–4.3 ppm (3a and 3b, $[\text{O}-\text{CH}_2]$) are consistent with the addition of epichlorohydrin to the aromatic diols. Concomitantly, the appearance of signals at 3.3 (4, [epoxy CH]) and 2.7–2.8 (5a and 5b); [epoxy CH_2]) ppm is consistent with the presence of closed epoxy rings in the intermediate diglycidyl ether compounds. In both spectra (Figure 2b,c), the sum of the integral values of different signals ($\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$: 3.35 for DGEBAF and 3.46 for DGEPhPhn; epoxy CH: 1.65 for DGEBAF and 1.69 for DGEPhPhn; epoxy CH_2 : 3.36 for both DGEBAF and DGEPhPhn) holds a proper ratio according to the theoretical structure (Scheme 2); however, it refers to a partial substitution of the hydroxyl groups (84–85%) when compared to the internal standards such as aromatic signals 2a and 2b (Figure 2). Signals at 5.5, 4.0, and 3.6–3.7 ppm account for the ring-opened products. The discrepancies in the integrations versus what would be expected from the idealized structures may be explained by a combination of incomplete addition of epichlorohydrin and incomplete epoxy ring formation, both of which are well-known side reactions during epichlorohydrin-based epoxidation. Based on the integrations obtained from the NMR spectra, the total yield of the reaction was estimated to be $\sim 70\%$.

Diglycidyl ethers (all synthesized as above except DGEBA, which was procured and used as received) were subjected to carbonation without further purification. After a second purification of the crude bis(cyclocarbonate) product through precipitation, it was possible to achieve the $\sim 99\%$ pure five-membered bis(cyclic carbonate) of bisphenol A (CCBA) with a yield of 96% (with respect to the initial moles of DGEBA) and $\sim 95\%$ pure products for CCBAF (bis(cyclic carbonate) of bisphenol AF) and CCPhPhn (bis(cyclic carbonate) of phenolphthalein) with a yield of $\sim 35\text{--}40\%$. The lower yields for CCBAF and CCPhPhn are ascribed to the lower levels of

conversion during the respective epoxidation reactions coupled with the loss of product during purification.

The structure and purity of bis(cyclic carbonate) monomers were assessed by ^1H NMR (Figures 2 and S5–S7) and IR (Figures 3 and S8, S9) spectroscopy as well as by elemental analysis. In the NMR spectrum of the as-prepared bis(cyclic carbonate) products, the disappearance of epoxy signals (4, 5a, and 5b, Figure 2) was found to be associated with a shift of ether signals from $\delta = 3.8\text{--}4.3$ ppm (3a and 3b, $[\text{O}-\text{CH}_2]$ in the spectra of diglycidyl ethers) to 4.2–4.3 ppm (6a and 6b, $[\text{O}-\text{CH}_2]$ in the bis(cyclic carbonate) spectra. At the same time, signals at 5.2 (7, [cyclocarbonate CH]) and 4.4–4.6 ppm (8a and 8b, [cyclocarbonate CH_2]) were assigned for the generation of five-membered carbonate rings in the products. The newly appeared signals in the spectra of bis(cyclic carbonate)s were found to hold a proper ratio of integral values (4.10:2.00:4.02 for $\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$ (cyclocarbonate), CH (cyclocarbonate), and CH_2 , respectively) corresponding to the cyclic carbonate structures and proper ratio with the internal standards of the aromatic system (2a and 2b, 8H). The correspondence of the integrations with the idealized structure is consistent with a high degree of conversion and a high purity of the obtained products. These results are fully in line with previous reports^{56,57} related to the synthesis of CCBA.

To support the NMR analysis, FTIR spectroscopy was also performed. The FTIR spectra of the bis(cyclic carbonate) monomers are shown in Figures 3 and S8 and S9. In the spectrum of the parent DGEBA, the signals associated with oxirane rings appear at 914 (*asym.* C–O–C stretching) and 830 (*sym.* C–O–C stretching) cm^{-1} . Other bands found at 1108 and 1035 cm^{-1} relate to aliphatic C–O–C bending and those at 1246 cm^{-1} are associated with aromatic (Ph–O–C) ether bond. A set of characteristic absorptions of aromatic rings is visible in the range of 1608–1510 and at 3055 cm^{-1} (Figure S8). Saturated alkyl groups give rise to medium C–H stretch bands between 2995 and 2838 cm^{-1} . Finally, the characteristic absorption of the ternary carbon (Ph–C(CH_3) $_2$ –Ph) appears as a sharp band at 1185 cm^{-1} .

The transformation of the oxirane rings in DGEBA to five-membered cyclic carbonates in CCBA is accompanied by the disappearance of bands at 914 and 830 cm^{-1} and their replacement by a new signal at 1789–1795 cm^{-1} that is assigned to the carbonyl stretch of carbonate groups (Figures 3 and S8). The disappearance of a signal at 830 cm^{-1} reveals the presence of another band with a significantly lower intensity at 826 cm^{-1} attributed to the CH bending of para-substituted aromatic rings. While all other mentioned characteristic bands remained at their positions, the conversion of epoxies to cyclocarbonates results in a slight decrease in intensity of the bands at 2983–2883 cm^{-1} attributed to the alkyl CH stretch.

Similar trends were observed in the FTIR spectra of CCBAF and CCPhPhn bis(cyclic carbonate)s (Figures 3 and S9). The characteristic signals of the epoxy groups disappeared after carbonation and were replaced by new signals of carbonate groups at 1795–1759 cm^{-1} . In addition, the IR spectrum of CCBAF shows bands at 1257 and 1134 cm^{-1} assigned to the presence of the CF_3 groups. In the spectrum of CCPhPhn, two overlapping carbonyl signals are observed (Figures 3 and S9). While as noted above the peak at 1795 cm^{-1} is assigned to the carbonyl stretch of the cyclocarbonate, the other band (at 1759 cm^{-1}) is attributed to the carbonyl stretch associated with the ester group (lactone cycle) internal to phenolphthalein. The

appearance of the latter signal confirms the integrity of the phenolphthalein substructure in CCPhPhn.

The synthesized CCBA monomer is a white crystalline powder which remains unchanged in appearance even after prolonged drying at 100 °C (as needed to remove the residual solvent following purification). The DSC analysis (Figure S10) of CCBA clearly showed a melting point of 159 °C during the first heating cycle. However, no crystallization was observed on cooling, and the second heating cycle demonstrated only the presence of single glass-transition temperature (T_g) at 32 °C (Figure S10). In contrast to CCBA, the CCBAF and CCPhPhn bis(cyclic carbonate)s melted during drying at 100 °C to yield beige and yellow solids, respectively, following purification. Reductions in drying temperature were not possible, as this led to incomplete solvent removal. The DSC traces for CCBAF and CCPhPhn (Figures S11 and S12) confirm the absence of any crystallization or melting processes and revealed only T_g values of 51 and 80 °C for CCBAF and CCPhPhn, respectively.

3.2. Optimization of Reaction Conditions for PHU Synthesis. PHUs were synthesized by reacting bis(cyclic carbonate)s and diamines under optimized conditions, as described in our previous report.³⁸ To evaluate the kinetics of the reaction, CCBA and HMDA were chosen as starting materials and were loaded into a twin-screw microcompounder along with 30 wt % of DMSO. The reaction time was varied from 1 to 270 min (4.5 h) to produce PHUs of different molecular weights. Confirming the lack of cross-linking, the resulting polymers were fully soluble in the following organic solvents: DMF, DMSO, NMP, and DMAc. Following the reaction, the polymers were purified and subjected to GPC/SEC analysis. Variations in molecular weight as a function of reaction time are shown in Figure 4, along with the respective

Figure 4. Variation of molecular weight and yield as a function of reaction time in the case of PHU formation from CCBA and HMDA via REX.

yields at each point. The yields were calculated by dividing the mass of the purified polymer by the total monomer mass and multiplying the ratio by 100. The molecular weight and the reaction yield were found to increase rapidly during the first 45 min, after which they reached a plateau. This apparent lack of progress beyond 45 min could be explained by trans-carbamoylation reactions^{14,58–60} and/or various other side reactions,¹⁸ as reported previously. When focusing on the early stages of the reaction, a time of only 5 min was observed to be sufficient to produce a molecular weight of 9700 g/mol ($M_w/M_n = 2.0$) and a yield of 30%. Longer reaction times (≥ 45

min) were found to be associated with polymers possessing molecular weights of 18000–20000 g/mol ($M_w/M_n = 1.9–2.0$) in yields of $\sim 65\%$. Repetition of the 270 min reaction produced minimal variations in molecular weight or yield, as indicated by the error bars shown in Figure 4 (1 standard deviation). Based on a detailed analysis of all previous experiments³⁸ and those presented in Figure 4, it can be concluded that the optimal reaction conditions for the synthesis of PHU with the highest possible molecular weight and in the highest yield are as follows: DMSO (as hydrogen bond disruptor), [CCBA + HMDA] = 77 wt %, [CCBA]/[HMDA] = 1:1 by mol, 100 °C, and 150 min (2.5 h).

3.3. PHUs Synthesized from CCBA and Different Diamines. Following the assessment of the effects of reaction time on the molecular weight and polymer yield, a new set of PHUs based on CCBA and different amines was synthesized (Figure 1 and Table 1). Low-melting-point (cyclo)aliphatic diamines were selected to ensure the homogeneity and high rate of the polyaddition. Moreover, the diamines were chosen to yield a broad-range molecular flexibility in the resultant PHUs. The optimal conditions determined previously for CCBA and HMDA reactions were applied for the synthesis of all PHUs in Table 1. In light of the different reactivity levels of the selected amines, the reactions were carried out for 270 min (4.5 h) to ensure completion, after which the polymers were purified and characterized. Once more confirming the lack of cross-linking, the resulting polymers were again fully soluble in the following organic solvents: DMF, DMSO, NMP, and DMAc. The values of number-average molecular weight (M_n), M_w/M_n ratio, yield, onset temperature of thermal degradation (T_{onset}), glass-transition temperature (T_g), and modulus at 25 °C for all PHUs are shown in Table 1.

After purification, all polymers were subjected to ^1H NMR analysis (Figures 5 and S15–S24). The ^1H NMR spectrum of the polymer produced by reacting CCBA with HMDA for 270 min is shown in Figure 5 as a representative example. In this ^1H NMR spectrum, the characteristic signals for HMDA ($\delta = 2.50$ ppm (17, 4H [N-CH₂])) and CCBA ($\delta = 5.1–5.2$ ppm (19, 2H, [cyclocarbonate CH]); 4.4–4.6 ppm (20 and 20*, 4H, [cyclocarbonate CH₂])) were absent. Concomitantly, new signals representing PU linkages ($\delta = 3.80–4.08$ ppm (3, 4, 5, and 6); 4.85 ppm (7, [hydroxyurethane OH-CH₂-CH]); 3.55 ppm (8, [hydroxyurethane HO-CH₂]), 2.92 ppm (10, [hydroxyurethane N-CH₂]), 7.13–7.20 ppm (9, [hydroxyurethane NH])) and hydroxyl units ($\delta = 4.90–5.19$ ppm (13 and 14, [OH])) were prominent in the spectrum. The ^1H NMR signals are in line with previous reports^{21,39,61} and consistent with the structures of the obtained PHUs as presented here. Applying the method of Schmidt et al.,³⁹ it was estimated from the ^1H NMR spectra that cyclocarbonate ring opening produced a secondary alcohol $\sim 74\%$ of the time, irrespective of the length of the reaction or the choice of precursors. The urea moieties often present as the result of side reactions in other PHUs at ~ 5.7 ppm³⁶ were absent in the polymer derived from CCBA and HMDA. Based on the integrations associated with the hydroxyl units (Figure 5, protons 13 and 14), a total ratio of primary to secondary hydroxyl groups of (OH)_I/(OH)_{II} = 26:74 was determined. The FTIR spectrum of the PHU based on CCBA and HMDA is shown in Figure S25. The majority of the bands attributed to CCBA are preserved, while the peak at 1795 cm⁻¹ assigned to the carbonyl stretch of the cyclic carbonate has been replaced by a new signal at 1701 cm⁻¹, attributed to the stretching of urethane's C=O group

Figure 5. ^1H NMR spectrum of the polymer produced via the reaction of CCBA with HMDA following a reaction time of 270 min, along with the spectra for the starting materials (top).

Figure 6. Chemical structures of the synthesized PHUs (a) and their DSC curves (b) revealing variations in T_g values as a function of the structural flexibility of selected amines and bis(cyclic carbonate)s (detailed DSC plots are provided in Figures S28–S35).

(amide I band). An amide II band (mixed vibration of N–H bending and C–N stretching) appears at 1535 cm^{-1} with an additional C–O bending absorption band at 1286 cm^{-1} . The intensity of the CH signals at $2936\text{--}2869\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is increased due to the presence of the aliphatic chains from HMDA. Finally, the characteristic bands of hydroxyl (OH) and amine (NH) groups appear at 3414 and 3331 cm^{-1} , respectively (Figure S25).

^1H NMR spectra of other PHUs produced from different combinations of CCBA and diamines are shown in the Supporting Information (Figures S18–S22). The ratio of primary to secondary hydroxyl groups of $(\text{OH})_{\text{I}}/(\text{OH})_{\text{II}}$ for this series of PHUs varied slightly but was generally close to 25:75 (Table S1). The only exception is the PHU based on CCBA and PACM, where a ratio of $(\text{OH})_{\text{I}}/(\text{OH})_{\text{II}} = 31:69$ was determined.

In the first part of Table 1, the amines reacted with CCBA have been listed in the order of increasing rigidity and decreasing size, both of which are expected to contribute to the increase in T_g of the resulting polymers. It should also be noted that the position of the amine functionalities will influence their nucleophilicity and reactivity toward bis(cyclic carbonate)s, as reported previously.¹³ In particular, when amines were attached to tertiary carbon atoms (as in PACM and IPDA, Table 1), they were found to produce PHUs with lower molecular weights (CCBA-PACM and CCBA-IPDA, $M_n = \sim 5000$ g/mol). All other amines provided considerably higher-molecular-weight PHUs ($M_n = 15000$ – 22000 g/mol). The fact that the highest molecular weight was observed for the PHU synthesized with DNDPA (CCBA-DNDPA; $M_n = 21800$ g/mol) might be explained by the presence of a tertiary amine group within the diamine monomer coupled with the fact that such groups are known to catalyze PHU synthesis.¹⁸

Regarding thermal stability, all PHUs gave $T_{\text{onset}} \geq 195$ °C, as shown in Table 1 and Figure S27, with the FADDA-based PHU being the most stable (CCBA-FADDA: $T_{\text{onset}} = 245$ °C), potentially due to the lower number of thermally unstable urethane groups in any given PHU chain. All the other CCBA-based PHUs (CCBA-DNDPA, CCBA-HMDA, CCBA-PACM, CCBA-*p*XDA, and CCBA-IPDA) showed similar degradation profiles with a T_{onset} of 195–210 °C.

In addition to thermal stability studies, the PHU samples were subjected to DSC analysis to observe all relevant thermal transitions (Figures S28–S33). The variations in T_g values as a function of amine type are shown in Figure 6b along with the chemical structures of the synthesized PHUs in Figure 6a. From these figures, it is evident that the variations in the T_g values of the synthesized polymers are in line with expectations as far as their dependence on the size and rigidity of the building blocks is concerned. While the PHU based on the most flexible diamine (CCBA-FADDA) displayed a T_g of 25 °C (Figure S28), moving to the shorter HMDA and DNDPA diamines results in increases in T_g to 58–59 °C (Table 1, Figures S29 and S30). The PHU based on *p*-XDA shows a higher T_g of 80 °C thanks to the rigidity of the aromatic ring. This PHU is further observed to be semicrystalline as well (Figure S31), displaying DSC endotherms at ~ 110 °C, attributed to the melting of the crystalline phase.⁶² Despite the higher number of carbons between amine functionalities, PACM produced PHU with a higher T_g than in the case of HMDA or *p*-XDA (CCBA-PACM: 97 °C vs CCBA-HMDA: 59 °C and CCBA-*p*-XDA: 80 °C). Similarly, the PHU based on cycloaliphatic IPDA gave the highest T_g of 101 °C (Figure S33). This is readily explained by the presence of rigid cyclohexyl moieties in the structures of both PACM and IPDA.

The T_a values, as measured by DMTA (Table 1), exhibited the same tendency as those measured by DSC, as shown in Figure 6b, though, as expected, they were slightly higher in absolute terms. In some cases (CCBA-PACM and CCBA-IPDA), the samples were too fragile to allow for DMTA measurements, however, possibly due to their low molecular weight.

Following molecular and thermal characterizations, the polymers based on CCBA were subjected to mechanical testing. The storage moduli at 25 °C obtained from DMTA plots (Figure S36) are shown in Table 1, while a representative plot (for CCBA-*p*XDA) is shown in Figure 7. The highest stiffness among the CCBA-based PHUs was observed for CCBA-DNDPA (2.1 GPa), though CCBA-HMDA and

Figure 7. Storage (E') and loss (E'') modulus curves for CCBA-*p*XDA PHU synthesized by REx (detailed DMTA plots are provided in Figure S36).

CCBA-*p*XDA provided modulus values almost as high as 1.42 GPa. As expected, the PHU based on the largest and most flexible amine, CCBA-FADDA, gave the lowest stiffness at room temperature (0.77 GPa). Similar observations were made during quasi-static mechanical testing, with stress–strain plots shown in Figure S37, and the average values for tensile strength, elongation at break, and tensile modulus are shown in Table 1. CCBA-FADDA gave the lowest tensile modulus (0.02 GPa) and tensile strength (8.82 ± 1.45 MPa) of the formulations tested, albeit with the highest elongation at break by far ($300 \pm 28\%$). In contrast, all other samples were brittle, with a maximum elongation of 2–3% before yield or failure. Among the CCBA-based samples, CCBA-DNDPA and CCBA-*p*XDA were the strongest, with CCBA-DNDPA displaying a tensile strength of 48.3 ± 7.0 MPa (tensile modulus, 2.53 ± 0.58 GPa) and CCBA-*p*XDA displaying a tensile strength of 43.19 ± 4.42 MPa (tensile modulus, 2.50 ± 0.33 GPa).

Taken in sum, these results show that *p*-XDA provides the properties targeted in the present study. Specifically, this work shows that a PHU based on CCBA and *p*-XDA (CCBA-*p*XDA) can be produced in good yield (80%) and with an acceptable molecular weight (~ 15000 g/mol), at which point it provides good thermal stability ($T_{\text{onset}} \sim 210$ °C), a T_g of 80 °C, a modulus (E') of ~ 1.4 GPa, and a tensile strength of ~ 43 MPa. Based on these considerations, *p*-XDA was selected as the diamine of choice to extend the study toward even higher T_g PHUs based on additional bis(cyclic carbonate)s.

3.4. PHUs Synthesized from *p*-XDA and Aromatic Bis(cyclic carbonate)s. Two more PHUs were synthesized by reacting the newly prepared bis(cyclic carbonate)s (CCBAF and CCPhPhn) with *p*-XDA. Following the synthesis, the polymers were purified and characterized in an analogous fashion to those described in the previous section, with the results shown in Table 1. The reaction of *p*-XDA with different bis(cyclic carbonate)s produced PHUs with broadly similar molecular weights ($M_n = 10000$ – 15000 g/mol with $M_w/M_n = 2$ – 3) and thermal stabilities ($T_{\text{onset}} = 210$ – 230 °C) to that of the analogous PHU derived from CCBA, in line with the structural similarities between the bis(cyclic carbonate)s chosen for the study. Concomitantly, the PHUs derived from bis(cyclic carbonate)s other than CCBA showed higher T_g values (102–110 °C via DSC) compared to their analogues

derived from CCBA (CCBA-*p*XDA: 80 °C via DSC). The difference may arise due to the structural rigidity of these bis(cyclic carbonate)s (CCBAF, CCPhPhn) compared to CCBA (Figure 1). NMR spectra and TGA and DSC plots for these materials appear in Supporting Information.

In addition to molecular and thermal characterizations, the *p*-XDA-based PHU samples were further subjected to mechanical testing. Again, bis(cyclic carbonate) selection produced substantial differences in mechanical response as well. Based on the DMTA data, CCPhPhn-*p*XDA gave a modulus of 2.9 GPa at 25 °C, versus 1.88 and 1.42 GPa for the same for CCBAF-*p*XDA and CCBA-*p*XDA, respectively. Tensile testing confirmed the high stiffness of both PHUs and revealed them to be the strongest of the polymers produced as well, with CCBAF-*p*XDA giving $E = 2.42 \pm 0.48$ GPa and $\sigma_t = 61.60 \pm 7.51$ MPa and CCPhPhn-*p*XDA giving $E = 3.39 \pm 0.36$ GPa and $\sigma_t = 56.0 \pm 1.5$ MPa.

Finally, in order to assess the processability of the *p*-XDA-based PHUs described here, frequency sweep experiments were carried out via parallel plate rheometry at 125 °C for CCBA-*p*XDA, CCBAF-*p*XDA, and CCPhPhn-*p*XDA, with the results (complex viscosity vs frequency) shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Complex viscosity as a function of angular frequency for a series of PHUs synthesized from *p*-XDA and different bis(cyclic carbonate)s.

Here, CCBA-*p*XDA and CCBAF-*p*XDA are observed to have similarly low complex viscosities as compared to CCPhPhn-*p*XDA. In line with these observations, CCBA-*p*XDA was found to be the easiest to process when fabricating thermoplastic PHU foams, as will be detailed in the following section.

3.5. Fabrication and Characterization of PHU Foams.

Following the characterization of the neat polymers, the three PHUs based on *p*-XDA were selected based on their high T_g values and attractive mechanical properties. These polymers were foamed using a vacuum compression molding device, and the properties of the resulting foams were evaluated. For the selected PHUs, foamability was found to be linked to complex viscosity. For example, with the lowest complex viscosity of the group, it was possible to foam CCBA-*p*XDA with greater ease compared to other synthesized PHUs and to produce foams with densities as low as ~ 0.035 g/cm³. In contrast, the lowest densities that could be achieved with CCBAF-*p*XDA and CCPhPhn-*p*XDA were ~ 0.06 and ~ 0.07 g/cm³, respectively. In order to aid in properties' comparisons, all three PHUs were foamed to a density of ~ 0.07 g/cm³, and the microstructure, mechanical properties, and thermal conductivity of the resulting materials were characterized.

To estimate the pore size distribution and cell structure, PHU foams were subjected to μ CT analysis. Pore size distributions obtained in this fashion for each of the three PHU foams are presented in Figure 9, alongside representative pictures and μ CT cross sections. From these analyses, the majority of the cells (>85%) were found to be interconnected, independent of the PHU type. The porosity (70–85 vol %) and pore size distribution (average pore size of 125–150 μ m and skewness of 35–50 μ m) were found to be broadly similar as well. Given these commonalities, all foams were expected to display similar performance characteristics.

Following morphological studies, PHU foams were subjected to quasi-static mechanical experiments (Table 2). As expected, these results show that similarities in porosity and pore size distribution lead to broadly similar mechanical performance as well, including stresses of 230–300 kPa at a compressive strain of 15% and compression set of 5–7%. These results are likewise quite comparable to that of

Figure 9. Foam morphology as obtained from μ CT (2D slice as inserts and pore size distributions) of a series of thermoplastic PHU foams based on *p*-XDA and different bis(cyclic carbonate) monomers (chemical structure represented for each case).

Table 2. Mechanical and Heat Insulation Properties of Foams From Linear PHUs

PHU	density (g/cm ³)	compressive properties		thermal transport properties	
		stress at 15% strain (kPa)	set (%)	conductivity (mW/m·K)	diffusivity (mm ² /s)
CCBA- <i>p</i> XDA	0.06 ± 0.01	300 ± 90	5.0 ± 0.4	47 ± 0.02	0.49 ± 0.04
CCBAF- <i>p</i> XDA	0.06 ± 0.01	250 ± 25	7.2 ± 2.5	43 ± 0.02	0.67 ± 0.13
CCPhPhn- <i>p</i> XDA	0.07 ± 0.01	230 ± 25	4.7 ± 0.6	47 ± 0.01	0.57 ± 0.06

conventional rigid PU foams (where a foam of density of 0.04 g/cm³ might produce a stress of 200 kPa at a compressive strain of 10%⁶³), which are the market leaders for packaging and thermal insulation applications. Anticipating such uses, the foams were subjected to thermal conductivity testing as well, with the results shown in Table 2. The thermal conductivity of the PHU foams was found to be in the range of 43–47 mW/m·K, while thermal diffusivity varied within the range of 0.5–0.6 mm²/s. The values are quite similar to the thermal conductivity of cross-linked PU foams (48 mW/m·K)⁶⁴ and expanded thermoplastic polystyrene (32 mW/m·K),⁶⁵ as reported previously. Considering the similar mechanical and thermal insulation properties of the newly fabricated thermoplastic PHU foams in comparison to traditional rigid thermoplastic PU foams, PHU foams provide clear advantages when the toxicity of the monomers is an important consideration.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A series of PHUs based on different diamines and bis(cyclic carbonate)s were designed and synthesized using REx. Linear polymers with molecular weights in the 10000–20000 g/mol range were obtained in a relatively short time. Notably, a 5 min reaction time was associated with a molecular weight of 9700 g/mol, while a reaction of ≥45 min resulted in molecular weights in the 18000–20000 g/mol range. The T_g value of the synthesized polymers was found to be strongly dependent on the choice of monomers. With a proper selection of diamines and bis(cyclic carbonate)s, it was possible to obtain PHUs with T_g values as high as 80–110 °C, high stiffness at room temperature, and reasonable thermal stability ($T_{onset} > 195$ °C). Tensile strengths as high as 40–60 MPa and tensile modulus as high as 2.4–3.4 GPa were observed when compact diamines were used, while a high elongation at break (~300%) could be realized using a larger, more flexible diamine monomer. The study was further extended by evaluating the potential applications of the synthesized polymers. Anticipating utility in packaging and thermal insulation, the thermoplastic PHUs based on *p*-XDA were foamed. The fabricated foams were of low density (~0.07 g/cm³) and possessed mechanical strength and thermal transport properties comparable to traditional rigid PU foams. Considering the environmental and production hazards linked to traditional PU foam formation, these newly fabricated PHU foams represent interesting alternative material solutions for thermal insulation and packaging industries.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.macromol.4c00222>.

NMR and FTIR spectra of diglycidyl ethers; NMR, FTIR, and DSC of bis(cyclic carbonate)s; photo of the Büchi glass high-pressure reactor with attached heating/

cooling thermostat and twin-screw microcompounder (reactive extruder) used for the synthesis of bis(cyclic carbonate)s and PHUs, respectively; NMR and FTIR spectra of PHUs; representation of vacuum compression molding device; TGA plots, DSC traces, DMTA plots, and stress–strain curves of PHUs synthesized by REx; detailed description of foaming instrument; and stress versus strain curves of PHU foams (PDF)

■ AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

Daniel F. Schmidt – Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), L-4362 Esch-sur-Alzette, Luxembourg; orcid.org/0000-0003-2511-1906; Phone: +352 275 888 4904; Email: daniel.schmidt@list.lu

Vincent Berthé – Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), L-4362 Esch-sur-Alzette, Luxembourg; orcid.org/0000-0003-4330-5325; Phone: +352 275 888 4527; Email: vincent.berthe@list.lu

Authors

Arpan Datta Sarma – Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), L-4362 Esch-sur-Alzette, Luxembourg; orcid.org/0000-0002-0464-8942

Sergei V. Zubkevich – Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), L-4362 Esch-sur-Alzette, Luxembourg; orcid.org/0000-0001-5371-0901

Frédéric Addiego – Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), L-4362 Esch-sur-Alzette, Luxembourg; orcid.org/0000-0002-4081-9526

Alexander S. Shaplov – Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), L-4362 Esch-sur-Alzette, Luxembourg; orcid.org/0000-0002-7789-2663

Complete contact information is available at: <https://pubs.acs.org/10.1021/acs.macromol.4c00222>

Funding

The work was supported by Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR) through project SAFFIA (agreement number INTER/MERA/20/15020254) in partnership with the companies FLOKSER KEMYA and TOFAŞ.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

■ ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR) through the SAFFIA project (INTER/MERA/20/15020254). The authors are thankful to Dr. Reiner Dieden, Benoit Marcolini, Régis Vaudémont, and Sébastien Gergen for their help and support to conduct NMR, thermal, and mechanical experiments, respectively. EVONIK Industries AG (Germany, Essen, <https://composites.evonik.com/en/products-services/coatings/VESTAMIN>) is gratefully acknowledged for supplying isophorone diamine (Vestamin

IPD, IPDA) and *p*-diamino dicyclohexyl methane (Vestamin PACM, PACM). Dr. Daniel Treffer and MeltPrep GmbH are acknowledged for their invaluable help with the design and production of the vacuum compression molding equipment for PHU foam fabrication.

REFERENCES

- (1) Yue, M.; Chian, K. S. Chapter 29 – Properties and Applications of Thermoplastic Polyurethane Blends. In *Advances in Engineering Fluid Mechanics: Multiphase Reactor and Polymerization System Hydrodynamics*; Cheremisinoff, N. P., Ed.; Gulf Professional Publishing: Burlington, 1996; pp 747–761.
- (2) Szycher, M. In *Szycher's Handbook of Polyurethanes*; Szycher, M., Ed.; CRC Press, 2012.
- (3) Cornille, A.; Michaud, G.; Simon, F.; Fouquay, S.; Auvergne, R.; Boutevin, B.; Caillol, S. Promising Mechanical and Adhesive Properties of Isocyanate-Free Poly(Hydroxyurethane). *Eur. Polym. J.* **2016**, *84*, 404–420.
- (4) Nohra, B.; Candy, L.; Blanco, J.-F.; Guerin, C.; Raoul, Y.; Mouloungui, Z. From Petrochemical Polyurethanes to Biobased Polyhydroxyurethanes. *Macromolecules* **2013**, *46* (10), 3771–3792.
- (5) Karol, M. H.; Kramarik, J. A. Phenyl Isocyanate Is a Potent Chemical Sensitizer. *Toxicol. Lett.* **1996**, *89* (2), 139–146.
- (6) Karol, M. H.; Ruzhi, J. Immunohistochemical Detection of Toluene Diisocyanate (Tdi) Adducts in Pulmonary Tissue of Guinea Pigs Following Inhalation Exposure. *Inhalation Toxicol.* **1997**, *9* (2), 63–84.
- (7) Kimber, I.; Dearman, R. J.; Basketter, D. A. Diisocyanates, Occupational Asthma and IgE Antibody: Implications for Hazard Characterization. *J. Appl. Toxicol.* **2014**, *34* (10), 1073–1077.
- (8) Annex XVII to REACH – Conditions of Restrictions on the Manufacture, Placing on the Market and Use of Certain Dangerous Substances, Mixtures and Articles (entry 74). 2020. <https://echa.europa.eu/substances-restricted-under-reach/-/dislist/details/0b0236e185347b62> (accessed June 14, 2023).
- (9) Maisonneuve, L.; Lamarzelle, O.; Rix, E.; Grau, E.; Cramail, H. Isocyanate-Free Routes to Polyurethanes and Poly(Hydroxyurethane). *S. Chem. Rev.* **2015**, *115* (22), 12407–12439.
- (10) Kim, H. C.; Mun, S.; Ko, H.-U.; Zhai, L.; Kafy, A.; Kim, J. Renewable Smart Mater. *Smart Mater. Struct.* **2016**, *25* (7), 073001.
- (11) Ghasemlou, M.; Daver, F.; Ivanova, E. P.; Adhikari, B. Bio-Based Routes to Synthesize Cyclic Carbonates and Polyamines Precursors of Non-Isocyanate Polyurethanes: A Review. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2019**, *118*, 668–684.
- (12) Rokicki, G.; Parzuchowski, P. G.; Mazurek, M. Non-Isocyanate Polyurethanes: Synthesis, Properties, and Applications. *Polym. Adv. Technol.* **2015**, *26* (7), 707–761.
- (13) Cornille, A.; Auvergne, R.; Figoisky, O.; Boutevin, B.; Caillol, S. A Perspective Approach to Sustainable Routes for Non-Isocyanate Polyurethanes. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2017**, *87*, 535–552.
- (14) Fortman, D. J.; Brutman, J. P.; Cramer, C. J.; Hillmyer, M. A.; Dichtel, W. R. Mechanically Activated, Catalyst-Free Polyhydroxyurethane Vitrimers. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137* (44), 14019–14022.
- (15) Schimpf, V.; Max, J. B.; Stolz, B.; Heck, B.; Müllhaupt, R. Semicrystalline Non-Isocyanate Polyhydroxyurethanes as Thermoplastics and Thermoplastic Elastomers and Their Use in 3D Printing by Fused Filament Fabrication. *Macromolecules* **2019**, *52* (1), 320–331.
- (16) Besse, V.; Foyer, G.; Auvergne, R.; Caillol, S.; Boutevin, B. Access to Nonisocyanate Poly(Thio)Urethanes: A Comparative Study. *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2013**, *51* (15), 3284–3296.
- (17) Besse, V.; Camara, F.; Méchin, F.; Fleury, E.; Caillol, S.; Pascault, J.-P.; Boutevin, B. How to Explain Low Molar Masses in PolyHydroxyUrethanes (PHUs). *Eur. Polym. J.* **2015**, *71*, 1–11.
- (18) Ecochard, Y.; Caillol, S. Hybrid Polyhydroxyurethanes: How to Overcome Limitations and Reach Cutting Edge Properties? *Eur. Polym. J.* **2020**, *137*, 109915.
- (19) Fortman, D. J.; Brutman, J. P.; Hillmyer, M. A.; Dichtel, W. R. Structural Effects on the Reprocessability and Stress Relaxation of Crosslinked Polyhydroxyurethanes. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **2017**, *134* (45), 44984.
- (20) Kihara, N.; Endo, T. Synthesis and Properties of Poly-(Hydroxyurethane). *S. J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **1993**, *31*, 2765–2773.
- (21) Ochiai, B.; Inoue, S.; Endo, T. One-Pot Non-Isocyanate Synthesis of Polyurethanes from Bisepoxide, Carbon Dioxide, and Diamine. *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2005**, *43* (24), 6613–6618.
- (22) Tomita, H.; Sanda, F.; Endo, T. Structural Analysis of Polyhydroxyurethane Obtained by Polyaddition of Bifunctional Five-Membered Cyclic Carbonate and Diamine Based on the Model Reaction. *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2001**, *39* (6), 851–859.
- (23) Kim, M.-R.; Kim, H.-S.; Ha, C.-S.; Park, D.-W.; Lee, J.-K. Syntheses and Thermal Properties of Poly(Hydroxy)Urethanes by Polyaddition Reaction of Bis(Cyclic Carbonate) and Diamines. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **2001**, *81* (11), 2735–2743.
- (24) Fache, M.; Darroman, E.; Besse, V.; Auvergne, R.; Caillol, S.; Boutevin, B. Vanillin, a promising biobased building-block for monomer synthesis. *Green Chem.* **2014**, *16* (4), 1987–1998.
- (25) Steblyanko, A.; Choi, W.; Sanda, F.; Endo, T. Addition of Five-Membered Cyclic Carbonate with Amine and Its Application to Polymer Synthesis. *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2000**, *38* (13), 2375–2380.
- (26) Benyahya, S.; Habas, J.-P.; Auvergne, R.; Lapinte, V.; Caillol, S. Structure-Property Relationships in Polyhydroxyurethanes Produced from Terephthaloyl Dicyclocarbonate with Various Polyamines. *Polym. Int.* **2012**, *61* (11), 1666–1674.
- (27) Beniah, G.; Liu, K.; Heath, W. H.; Miller, M. D.; Scheidt, K. A.; Torkelson, J. M. Novel Thermoplastic Polyhydroxyurethane Elastomers as Effective Damping Materials over Broad Temperature Ranges. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2016**, *84*, 770–783.
- (28) Zhang, L.; Luo, X.; Qin, Y.; Li, Y. A Novel 2,5-Furandicarboxylic Acid-Based Bis(Cyclic Carbonate) for the Synthesis of Biobased Non-Isocyanate Polyurethanes. *RSC Adv.* **2017**, *7* (1), 37–46.
- (29) Prömpers, G.; Keul, H.; Höcker, H. Polyurethanes with Pendant Hydroxy Groups: Polycondensation of D-Mannitol-1,2:5,6-Dicarbonate with Diamines. *Des. Monomers Polym.* **2005**, *8* (6), 547–569.
- (30) Janvier, M.; Ducrot, P.-H.; Allais, F. Isocyanate-Free Synthesis and Characterization of Renewable Poly(Hydroxy)Urethanes from Syringaresinol. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2017**, *5* (10), 8648–8656.
- (31) Chen, Q.; Gao, K.; Peng, C.; Xie, H.; Zhao, Z. K.; Bao, M. Preparation of Lignin/Glycerol-Based Bis(Cyclic Carbonate) for the Synthesis of Polyurethanes. *Green Chem.* **2015**, *17* (9), 4546–4551.
- (32) Eltayeb, M.; Li, S.; Okoye, P. U.; Wang, S. Carbodiimide-Assisted Synthesis of High Purity Bis(Cyclic Carbonate) Under Atmospheric Conditions for Preparation of Non-Isocyanate Polyurethane. *J. Polym. Environ.* **2021**, *29* (6), 1880–1893.
- (33) Benyahya, S.; Boutevin, B.; Caillol, S.; Lapinte, V.; Habas, J.-P. Optimization of the Synthesis of Polyhydroxyurethanes Using Dynamic Rheometry. *Polym. Int.* **2012**, *61* (6), 918–925.
- (34) Blain, M.; Cornille, A.; Boutevin, B.; Auvergne, R.; Benazet, D.; Andrioletti, B.; Caillol, S. Hydrogen Bonds Prevent Obtaining High Molar Mass PHUs. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **2017**, *134* (45), 44958.
- (35) Blain, M.; Jean-Gérard, L.; Auvergne, R.; Benazet, D.; Caillol, S.; Andrioletti, B. Rational Investigations in the Ring Opening of Cyclic Carbonates by Amines. *Green Chem.* **2014**, *16* (9), 4286–4291.
- (36) Magliozzi, F.; Chollet, G.; Grau, E.; Cramail, H. Benefit of the Reactive Extrusion in the Course of Polyhydroxyurethanes Synthesis by Aminolysis of Cyclic Carbonates. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2019**, *7* (20), 17282–17292.
- (37) Delebecq, E.; Pascault, J.-P.; Boutevin, B.; Ganachaud, F. On the Versatility of Urethane/Urea Bonds: Reversibility, Blocked

Isocyanate, and Non-Isocyanate Polyurethane. *Chem. Rev.* **2013**, *113* (1), 80–118.

(38) Zubkevich, S. V.; Makarov, M.; Dieden, R.; Puchot, L.; Berthé, V.; Westermann, S.; Shaplov, A. S.; Schmidt, D. F. *Macromolecules* **2024**, *57* (5), 2385–2393.

(39) Schmidt, S.; Gatti, F. J.; Luitz, M.; Ritter, B. S.; Bruchmann, B.; Müllhaupt, R. Erythritol Dicarboxylate as Intermediate for Solvent- and Isocyanate-Free Tailoring of Bio-Based Polyhydroxyurethane Thermoplastics and Thermoplastic Elastomers. *Macromolecules* **2017**, *50* (6), 2296–2303.

(40) Hopmann, C.; Adamy, M.; Cohnen, A. Introduction to Reactive Extrusion. In *Reactive Extrusion: Principles and Applications*; John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2017, pp 1–10.

(41) Poussard, L.; Mariage, J.; Grignard, B.; Detrembleur, C.; Jérôme, C.; Calberg, C.; Heinrichs, B.; De Winter, J.; Gerbaux, P.; Raquez, J.-M.; Bonnaud, L.; Dubois, P. Non-Isocyanate Polyurethanes from Carbonated Soybean Oil Using Monomeric or Oligomeric Diamines To Achieve Thermosets or Thermoplastics. *Macromolecules* **2016**, *49* (6), 2162–2171.

(42) Subbotina, E.; Montanari, C.; Olsén, P.; Berglund, L. A. Fully Bio-Based Cellulose Nanofiber/Epoxy Composites with Both Sustainable Production and Selective Matrix Deconstruction towards Infinite Fiber Recycling Systems. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2022**, *10* (2), 570–576.

(43) Ma, S.; Wei, J.; Jia, Z.; Yu, T.; Yuan, W.; Li, Q.; Wang, S.; You, S.; Liu, R.; Zhu, J. Readily Recyclable, High-Performance Thermosetting Materials Based on a Lignin-Derived Spiro Diacetal Trigger. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2019**, *7* (3), 1233–1243.

(44) Salazkin, S. N.; Vinogradova, S. V.; Komarova, L. I. Structure of the Product of the Reaction of Phenolphthalein with Epichlorohydrin. *Russ. Chem. Bull.* **1973**, *22*, 143–144.

(45) Kihara, N.; Hara, N.; Endo, T. Catalytic Activity of Various Salts in the Reaction of 2,3-Epoxypropyl Phenyl Ether and Carbon Dioxide under Atmospheric Pressure. *J. Org. Chem.* **1993**, *58* (23), 6198–6202.

(46) Camara, F.; Benyahya, S.; Besse, V.; Boutevin, G.; Auvergne, R.; Boutevin, B.; Caillol, S. Reactivity of Secondary Amines for the Synthesis of Non-Isocyanate Polyurethanes. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2014**, *55*, 17–26.

(47) Rieger, J. The Glass Transition Temperature T_g of Polymers—Comparison of the Values from Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA, DSC) and Dynamic Mechanical Measurements (Torsion Pendulum). *Polym. Test.* **2001**, *20* (2), 199–204.

(48) Lei, Z.; Xing, W.; Wu, J.; Huang, G.; Wang, X.; Zhao, L. The Proper Glass Transition Temperature of Amorphous Polymers on Dynamic Mechanical Spectra. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* **2014**, *116* (1), 447–453.

(49) Berthe, V.; Shaplov, A.; Zubkevich, S.; Datta Sarma, A. Method for Producing Thermoplastic Polyurethane (PU) Foams. LU 505106, 2023.

(50) Depaifve, S.; Hermans, S.; Ruch, D.; Laachachi, A. Combination of Micro-Computed X-Ray Tomography and Electronic Microscopy to Understand the Influence of Graphene Nanoplatelets on the Thermal Conductivity of Epoxy Composites. *Thermochim. Acta* **2020**, *691*, 178712.

(51) Ghosh, A.; Sen, S. K.; Banerjee, S.; Voit, B. Solubility Improvements in Aromatic Polyimides by Macromolecular Engineering. *RSC Adv.* **2012**, *2* (14), 5900–5926.

(52) Hsiao, S.-H.; Chiang, H.-W. Synthesis and Structure-Property Study of Polyarylates Derived from Bisphenols with Different Connector Groups. *J. Polym. Res.* **2005**, *12* (3), 211–218.

(53) Korshak, V. V.; Vinogradova, S. V.; Vygodskii, Y. S. Cardo Polymers. *J. Macromol. Sci., Part C* **1974**, *11* (1), 45–142.

(54) Vinogradova, S. V.; Salazkin, S. N.; Chelidze, G. Sh. *Plast. Massy* **1971**, *8*, 10.

(55) Carta, M.; Croad, M.; Jansen, J. C.; Bernardo, P.; Clarizia, G.; McKeown, N. B. Synthesis of cardo-polymers using Tröger's base formation. *Polym. Chem.* **2014**, *5* (18), 5255–5261.

(56) Gupta, A.; Singhal, R.; Nagpal, A. K. Reactive Blends of Epoxy Resin (DGEBA) Crosslinked by Anionically Polymerized Polycaprolactam: Process of Epoxy Cure and Kinetics of Decomposition. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **2004**, *92* (2), 687–697.

(57) Sukumaran Nair, A.; Cherian, S.; Balachandran, N.; Panicker, U. G.; Kalambayil Sankaranarayanan, S. K. Hybrid Poly(Hydroxy Urethane)s: Folded-Sheet Morphology and Thermoreversible Adhesion. *ACS Omega* **2019**, *4* (8), 13042–13051.

(58) Zheng, N.; Fang, Z.; Zou, W.; Zhao, Q.; Xie, T. Thermoset Shape-Memory Polyurethane with Intrinsic Plasticity Enabled by Transcarbamoylation. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2016**, *55* (38), 11421–11425.

(59) Yang, Y.; Urban, M. W. Self-Healing of Glucose-Modified Polyurethane Networks Facilitated by Damage-Induced Primary Amines. *Polym. Chem.* **2017**, *8* (1), 303–309.

(60) Vidil, T.; Llevot, A. Fully Biobased Vitrimers: Future Direction toward Sustainable Cross-Linked Polymers. *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2022**, *223* (13), 2100494.

(61) Ochiai, B.; Satoh, Y.; Endo, T. Polyaddition of Bifunctional Cyclic Carbonate with Diamine in Ionic Liquids: In Situ Ion Composite Formation and Simple Separation of Ionic Liquid. *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2009**, *47* (18), 4629–4635.

(62) Kajiyama, T.; MacKnight, W. J. Thermal Properties of Polyurethanes. Enthalpies and Entropies of Fusion. *Polym. J.* **1970**, *1* (5), 548–554.

(63) Elbers, N.; Ranaweera, C. K.; Ionescu, M.; Wan, X.; Kahol, P. K.; Gupta, R. K. Synthesis of Novel Biobased Polyol via Thiol-Ene Chemistry for Rigid Polyurethane Foams. *J. Renewable Mater.* **2017**, *5* (1), 74–83.

(64) Pau, D. S. W.; Fleischmann, C. M.; Spearpoint, M. J.; Li, K. Y. Thermophysical Properties of Polyurethane Foams and Their Melts. *Fire Mater.* **2014**, *38* (4), 433–450.

(65) Jannot, Y.; Schaefer, S.; Degiovanni, A.; Bianchin, J.; Fierro, V.; Celzard, A. A New Method for Measuring the Thermal Conductivity of Small Insulating Samples. *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **2019**, *90* (5), 54901.